

Vapor–Liquid Equilibria of Novel Pyrazolium Ionic Liquids with Alkyl Anions and Acetone

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ABSTRACT: Isobaric vapor–liquid equilibria of 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium thiocyanate ($[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{SCN}]$), 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide ($[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]$), 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tricyanomethanide ($[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]$), and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetracyanoborate ($[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]$), with water and ethanol were measured over the whole concentration range at 0.1, 0.07, and 0.05 MPa. Activity coefficients were estimated from the boiling temperatures of the binary systems, and the data were used to evaluate the ability of COSMO-RS for describing these molecular systems. Aiming at further understanding the molecular interactions on these systems, molecular dynamics

(MD) simulations were performed. On the basis of the interpretation of the radial and spatial distribution functions along with coordination numbers obtained through MD simulations, the effect of the increase of CN-groups in the IL anion in its capability to establish hydrogen bonds with water and ethanol was evaluated. The results obtained suggest that, for both water and ethanol systems, the anion $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ presents the higher ability to establish favorable interactions due to its charge, and that the ability of the anions to interact with the solvent, decreases with further increasing of the number of cyano groups in the anion. The ordering of the partial charges in the nitrogen atoms from the CN-groups in the anions agrees with the ordering obtained for VLE and activity coefficient data.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ethanol–water^{1,2} system, found on the fermentation broth of the production of bioethanol, is of major economical relevance. It has been the subject of considerable number of studies³ aiming at achieving an effective and economical separation process for the recovery of ethanol from the reacting media. In the field of separation processes, extractive distillation is the most common method for the separation of azeotropic or close-boiling mixtures. This process is based on the addition of another solvent, the entrainer, with high boiling point, that alters the relative volatility of the components enabling their separation.^{3–5} The search for the best entrainer for the ethanol–water system has been the focus of attention of several research groups.^{5–7} During the past decade, ionic liquids (ILs) have been studied as entrainers for extractive distillation having advantages over common organic compounds.^{2,3,5} Ionic liquids possess unique properties, as for instance, good solvation capacity to dissolve a broad variety of compounds, a wide liquidus range, extremely low vapor pressures, and they are easy to recover and reuse. They are usually composed of large organic cations and inorganic or organic anions, with

asymmetric structure and high charge dispersion at least on one of the ions. Through the combination

of different cations and anions⁸ it is possible to fine-tune their properties for specific applications, arising as suitable candidates to successfully replace common volatile organic compounds in different separation processes.^{3–5,9}

The assessment of the applicability of an IL to act as entrainer in different azeotropic systems is usually made through vapor pressure, boiling temperature or through activity coefficient data. Vapor–liquid equilibria (VLE), along with activity coefficient data, allow the evaluation of the potential of excess Gibbs energy (G^E) models, widely used for the description of the nonideal behavior of these systems. Hence, the possibility of two-phase formation and the type/strength of the interactions established between IL and water/ethanol can be gauged and a separation process designed.^{3,5,10}

Although object of interest during the past decade, limited research on VLE with ILs as entrainers for azeotropic separations has been reported.⁵ Seiler et al.,⁹ Jork et al.,¹¹ Beste et al.,¹² and Lei et al.¹³ were among the first to show

the use of ILs for separation of azeotropic mixtures. Revelli et al.¹⁴

reported some binary mixtures containing imidazolium-based ILs with light alcohols. In the open literature, there are reports of several imidazolium-based ILs investigated for the extractive distillation of ethanol–water mixtures.^{1,2,14–25} These studies focused on showing that the ILs may allow breaking the azeotrope, and on validating different procedures to measure VLE data with ILs. Ge et al.¹ and Orchilles et al.²⁴ compared and discussed the performance of the anions $[\text{Cl}]^-$, $[\text{Ac}]^-$, $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$, and $[\text{BF}_4]^-$ that they have been found to be the most suitable for an effective extractive distillation, according to the effect that they induce in the relative volatility of the system, which is also discussed in detail in the review of Pereiro et al.⁵ The ILs with the anions $[\text{Ac}]^-$ and $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ stand as the best candidates, not only due to their high propensity to interact favorably with water/ethanol, but also due to their lower viscosity (when comparing with the IL with the anion chloride) which enhance the mass transfer efficiency of the extractive distillation²⁶ or thermal stability when compared with $[\text{BF}_4]^-$.²⁷ The strong effect of water upon the viscosity of the ILs may further enhance this aspect and must be taken into account in the design of extraction processes.²⁸

The experimental determination of VLE data, aiming at disclosing the ILs activity–structure relationship, is an impractical task if one takes into account the large number of potential ILs that can be prepared by the combination of available cations and anions. To overcome this difficulty, semiempirical group contribution models (such as UNIFAC²⁹) and equations of state (such as PC-SAFT^{18,30,31}) are commonly applied to correlate experimental data aiming at predicting other systems not previously studied, or predictive models such as COSMO-RS^{10,32–35} have been used to scan the ILs in the quest for the best entrainers. Process simulators, such as Aspen Plus, can then be applied for an evaluation of the process and its optimization.^{3,26}

Additionally, the use of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations has also been reported.^{36,37} This computational approach based on statistical mechanics and Newton's equation of motion, allows the description of real systems at the atomic level, providing an understanding of the molecular interactions that take place.³⁸ This approach has the advantage of being capable to describe the dynamic behavior of systems, as well as, to predict its thermodynamic and transport properties.³⁹

Regarding the large variety of ILs, cyano-based ILs present a set of properties of great interest like low melting points and low viscosities,⁴⁰ and a surprisingly wide

hydrogen bond ability presenting themselves either as good solvents for carbohydrates (e.g., when the IL anion is $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$), or as water immiscible (e.g., when the IL anion is $[\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]^-$). They have been studied for many specific applications, namely electrolytes and dye-sensitized solar cells,^{41,42} extracting solvent for added-value compounds in biomass (phenolic compounds,⁴³ carbohydrates,^{44,45} and sugar alcohols⁴⁶) and aromatic–aliphatic separations¹⁰ and were also shown to successfully extract alcohols from fermentation broth.^{1,10,47}

In the present work, the binary systems composed of water or ethanol with imidazolium-based ILs, with anions containing an increasing number of CN-groups, were investigated. A systematic experimental study of the isobaric VLE, at pressures ranging from 0.05 to 0.1 MPa, along with the measurement of density and viscosity of the binary mixtures were performed. Additionally, COSMO-RS was evaluated on its ability to describe the studied systems and MD simulations were used aiming at understanding the molecular level interactions responsible for the macroscopic phase behavior of these systems.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Materials. Four imidazolium-based ILs with cyano containing anions were studied in this work, namely 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium thiocyanate, $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{SCN}]$, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide, $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]$, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tricyanomethanide, $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]$ that were acquired from IoLiTec (Germany) and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetracyanoborate, $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]$, from Merck KGaA Germany, all with mass fraction purities higher than 98%. The ILs chemical structures are shown in Table 1. To reduce both water and volatile compounds in the ILs to negligible values, vacuum (10^{-2} mbar), stirring, and moderate temperature (303 K) for a period of at least 48 h were applied prior to the measurements. ILs were also kept under vacuum (10^{-2} mbar) between uses. The final IL water content was determined with a Metrohm 831 Karl Fischer coulometer (using the Hydranal–Coulomat E from Riedel-de Haen as analyte), indicating a water mass fraction lower than 30×10^{-6} wt %. The purities of each IL were further checked by ¹H and ¹³C NMR.

The ethanol used was obtained from Merck with mass fraction purity higher than 99.8%. Being highly hygroscopic, the ethanol was kept with molecular sieves to ensure a low water content. The ethanol–water content measured was lower than 50×10^{-5} wt %. The water used was double distilled and deionized, passed through a reverse osmosis system and further treated with a Milli-Q plus 185 water purification equipment.

2.2. VLE Measurement. Apparatus and Procedures. VLE measurements were made with an isobaric

microebulliometer at different pressures: 0.05, 0.07, and 0.1 MPa. The apparatus used and the methodology adopted in this work have been previously optimized and are described in detail elsewhere.¹⁵ The equilibrium temperature of the liquid phase was measured, with an uncertainty of 0.2 K, with a fast response glass-sealed Pt100 class 1/10, which was calibrated prior to the measurements by comparison with a NIST-certified Fluke RTD25 standard thermometer, with an uncertainty less than 2×10^{-2} K. The internal pressure of the ebulliometer was kept constant through a vacuum pump Buchi V-700 and a V-850 Buchi pressure monitoring and controller unit. The system pressure was monitored by a MKS, model 728A, Baratron type capacitance manometer, with temperature regulation at 100 °C to avoid solvent condensation and with an accuracy of 0.5%. Only when the equilibrium temperature was constant for 30 min or longer, the equilibrium conditions were assumed. The mixture composition was determined through an Anton Paar Abbemat 500 Refractometer, with an uncertainty of 2×10^{-5} nD, using a calibration curve previously established. The adequacy of the apparatus to measure this type of systems was previously confirmed.¹⁵ Additionally, to test the apparatus, measurements of the VLE of pure compounds (ethanol, water, p-xylene, and decane) covering the temperature range of interest for the water + IL and ethanol + IL systems studied in this work were carried out. It was observed an uncertainty in the boiling temperatures of 0.2 K.

2.3. Density Measurement (Ethanol + IL Systems). In this work, mixtures of $[C_4C_{1im}][SCN]$, $[C_4C_{1im}][N(CN)_2]$, $[C_4C_{1im}][C(CN)_3]$, and $[C_2C_{1im}][B(CN)_4]$ with ethanol were prepared gravimetrically, with an uncertainty of $\pm 10^{-5}$ g, for subsequent measurement of density. In order to guarantee homogenization, mixtures were kept at constant stirring for 24 h, at room temperature in closed vials to minimize moisture absorption.

An automated SVM 3000 Anton Paar rotational Stabinger viscosimeter–densimeter was used to measure density data, at atmospheric pressure and at the temperature of 298.15 K. The viscosimeter–densimeter equipment uses Peltier elements for fast and efficient thermostatisation, and has been widely used by us^{40,48–50} for other systems composed of ILs. The uncertainty in temperature is within ± 0.02 K and the absolute uncertainty for density is $\pm 0.5 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. Obtained density data are compiled in Table S1 at the Supporting Information.

3. COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

3.1. COSMO-RS. COSMO-RS combines the advantages and the computational efficiency of the quantum chemical dielectric continuum solvation model COSMO with a statistical thermodynamics approach, based on the results of the quantum chemical calculations.^{51,52} The standard

procedure of COSMORS calculations consists of two steps. First, the software TURBOMOLE 6.1 program package at the RI-DFT BP/TZVP level was used for the quantum-chemical calculation to generate the COSMO files for each studied compound. And second COSMO-RS calculations were performed in the COSMOtherm software using the parameter file BP_TZVP_C21_0110 (COSMologic GmbH & Co KG, Leverkusen, Germany).^{51,52} Following the two-step procedure, COSMO-RS model has proved to be an excellent tool to evaluate qualitatively the strength of the interactions established by ILs with other compounds (binary or ternary systems), and consequently to predict their VLE,^{32,35,53,54} activity coefficients,^{55–58} liquid–liquid equilibria (LLE),^{59–61} among other properties.⁶² Therefore, COSMO-RS is going to be evaluated in the prediction of the experimental VLE data, and used to further understand the molecular level interactions as discussed below.

3.2. Molecular Dynamics Simulation. Molecular dynamics simulations were performed with the GROMACS⁶³ code, version 4.5.4, for the binary mixtures composed of ethanol and $[C_4C_{1im}][SCN]$, $[C_4C_{1im}][N(CN)_2]$, $[C_4C_{1im}][C(CN)_3]$, and $[C_2C_{1im}][B(CN)_4]$, at IL mole fractions of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8.

For all systems considered, after energy minimization and equilibration runs, production runs of 10 ns, within the canonical ensemble (NVT), were performed using a time step of 2 fs. The latter were followed by production runs of 20 ns, within the isothermal–isobaric (NPT) ensemble, at constant temperature of 298.15 K maintained using the Nose–Hoover^{64,65} thermostat, and at constant pressure of 1 bar maintained with the Parrinello–Rahman⁶⁶ barostat. The intermolecular interaction energy between pairs of neighboring atoms was calculated using the Lennard-Jones and the pointcharge Coulomb potentials for describing dispersion/repulsion and electrostatic forces, respectively. Lennard-Jones and Coulombic interactions were defined setting the cutoffs to 1.2 and 1.0 nm, respectively, and long-range corrections for energy and pressure were also applied. Rigid constraints were enforced on all bonds lengths.

The force field parameters for the $[C_4C_{1im}]^+$ and $[C_2C_{1im}]^+$ cations, as well as for the $[SCN]^-$ anion were published in our previous work.⁶⁷ The potential parameters for the $[N(CN)_2]^-$ and $[C(CN)_3]^-$ anions were taken from the OPLS-AA force field,^{68,69} and the $[B(CN)_4]^-$ anion were taken from the work

of Koller et al.⁷⁰ The atomic charges for the IL cations and anions were recalculated with the CHelpG scheme⁷¹ using an optimized geometry (minimum energy among different configurations), for each IL ion pair, in the gaseous phase as performed previously for other systems involving ILs.^{39,67} The calculations were performed at the B3LYP/6-311+G(d)

level of theory⁷² using the Gaussian 09 code.⁷³ The total charges on the cations and anions were ± 0.804 e for $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{SCN}]$, ± 0.826 e for $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]$, ± 0.882 e for $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]$ and ± 0.889 e for $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]$. The full sets of atomic charges for each IL were reported elsewhere.⁷⁴ The parameters for ethanol were also taken from the OPLS-AA force field.^{68,69}

For validation of the applied force field, density and enthalpy of vaporization were calculated. The latter was obtained according to eq 1,

$$\Delta H_{\text{vap}} = -RT (U_{\text{liq}} - U_{\text{vap}}) \quad (1)$$

where ΔH^{vap} is the enthalpy of vaporization, R is the ideal gas constant, T is the temperature, and U^{vap} and U^{liq} are the molar internal energies of the gaseous and of the liquid phases, respectively. To reproduce the gas phase, isolated IL ion pairs were considered and simulations were performed at the same temperature of the liquid phase.

In addition, radial and spatial distributions functions and coordination numbers were also calculated from the MD trajectories of all mixtures considered.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. VLE Measurements and COSMO-RS Predictions. Isobaric VLE data of the binary systems $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{SCN}]$, $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]$, $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]$ and $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]$ with water and ethanol were measured at 0.1, 0.07, and 0.05 MPa, and are reported in Table 2 to 8 and depicted in Figure 1 and 2 along with the COSMO-RS predictions. The experimental boiling temperature is represented as a function of the mole fraction of water/ethanol and compared with the COSMO-RS predictions, in the region of complete miscibility.

The COSMO-RS model prediction for the binary system $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{SCN}]$, $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]$, $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]$, and $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]$ with water and ethanol is found to be in close agreement with the experimental boiling points for mole fractions higher than 0.8. Afterward, the quality of the predictions degrades with the ILs concentration, for which only a qualitative prediction is achieved, as observed in previous works.^{55,75}

For the studied systems, and to the best of our knowledge, the VLE data is here reported for the first time. Orchilles et al.²⁵

Table 5. Experimental Isobaric VLE Data for the System $[C_4C_{1im}][SCN]$ (1) + Ethanol (2) at (0.1, 0.07, and 0.05) MPa Pressures^a

0.1 MPa			0.07 MPa			0.05 MPa		
x_2	T/K	γ_2	x_2	T/K	γ_2	x_2	T/K	γ_2
	351.15	0.999		342.36	0.999		334.63	0.996
0.982	351.49	0.996	0.981	342.71	1.006	0.982	334.98	0.996
0.981	351.58	0.994	0.979	342.93	0.997	0.973	335.16	1.000
0.963	351.98	0.997	0.963	343.24	1.001	0.961	335.60	0.993
0.943	352.07	1.014	0.943	343.65	1.004	0.933	336.36	0.989
0.921	352.54	1.019	0.919	344.15	1.009	0.914	336.84	0.989
0.892	353.60	1.015	0.897	344.82	1.007	0.895	337.33	0.989
0.870	354.38	1.010	0.850	346.60	0.988	0.871	338.27	0.976
0.834	355.61	1.005	0.832	347.44	0.975	0.840	339.41	0.963
0.794	357.46	0.984	0.807	348.72	0.954	0.795	341.42	0.934
0.781	358.17	0.968	0.790	349.53	0.945	0.775	342.53	0.914
0.767	358.97	0.956	0.770	350.44	0.934	0.759	343.40	0.901
0.693	362.96	0.911	0.690	355.06	0.870	0.698	346.71	0.855
0.675	363.98	0.898	0.681	355.50	0.867	0.681	347.91	0.835
0.628	366.62	0.878	0.623	358.82	0.836	0.628	350.64	0.811
0.593	368.91	0.867	0.584	360.90	0.825	0.595	352.53	0.795
0.570	370.73	0.846	0.572	362.18	0.804	0.570	354.33	0.774
0.531	373.01	0.841	0.523	365.63	0.775	0.530	356.71	0.759
0.501	374.93	0.836	0.416	372.71	0.760	0.490	359.18	0.749
0.407	382.38	0.806	0.399	375.08	0.732	0.424	364.45	0.714
0.344	388.81	0.778	0.350	379.50	0.720	0.360	370.15	0.687
0.313	392.38	0.766	0.315	383.06	0.712	0.333	372.45	0.684
0.241	402.38	0.740	0.243	391.97	0.700	0.282	377.45	0.680

^a γ are 0.001, 0.2 K, and 0.001, respectively.

Standard uncertainties x , T , and

reported VLE data for the binary mixture for $[C_2C_{1im}][N(CN)_2]$ with water and ethanol that, in comparison with that of $[C_4C_{1im}][N(CN)_2]$, denotes the well-established weak cation influence on the systems boiling temperatures, within the range of mole fraction investigated, as depicted in the Supporting Information (Figure S1). The isobaric VLE data for $[C_4C_{1im}][SCN]$ + water at 0.1, 0.07, and 0.05 MPa was adapted from Passos et al.,¹⁸ Figure 1 and 2 report the VLE of the studied systems as a function of composition, temperature and pressure. It can be seen that pressure does not have a strong influence on the shape of the boiling-point elevation dependency with the concentration, as shown by the parallel behavior of the temperature–composition equilibrium curves at the different pressures (for variation of activity coefficient see Supporting Information, Figure S2).

The measured boiling temperatures decrease with increasing solvent concentration as expected and shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3, and the influence of ILs on the boiling

temperature of both water and ethanol seems to follow the trend, $[C_4C_{1im}][N(CN)_2] > [C_4C_{1im}][SCN] > [C_4C_{1im}][C(CN)_3]$

$> [C_2C_{1im}][B(CN)_4]$, which is identical to the trend of mutual solubility of water and $[C_4C_{1pyr}]^+$ -based ILs reported by Krolikowska et al.⁷⁶

It is well established that the anion plays a primordial role in the IL interaction with water.^{77–79} Regarding the studied ILs, the imidazolium cation was fixed with the aim of studying the differentiation between the anions interactions with water and ethanol. The hydrogen bonding capability of the cyano group with water/ethanol was expected to increase with the number of cyano groups in the anion. However, although the expected increase on the number of interaction positions is observed for $[C_4C_{1im}][SCN]$ and $[C_4C_{1im}][N(CN)_2]$, the reversed behavior with further increase of the number of cyano groups is perceived for the other two compounds in the anion series $[C(CN)_3]^-$ and $[B(CN)_4]^-$. As shown in recent work,⁷⁴ using COSMO-RS

(sigma profile and potential), the high polarity of the anion $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ leads to a higher capability to establish hydrogen bonds (H-bond donors) than $[\text{SCN}]^-$. In that work it was found also that by increasing the number of cyano groups from $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ to $[\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]^-$ and to $[\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]^-$, the ability of these anions to act as H-bond acceptors decrease. As a consequence, it is expected that $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ presents stronger interactions with water/ethanol than $[\text{SCN}]^-$, $[\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]^-$ and $[\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]^-$ besides the lower number of the interaction position/groups could be interpreted as a consequence of the change in their charge distribution due to the partial geometric dipole moment cancelation.

4.1.1. Activity Coefficients. The effect of an IL on the nonideality of a solution can be expressed by the activity coefficient of component i , γ_i , which can be estimated from the vapor liquid equilibrium data by the equation

$$\gamma_i = y_i p / x_i \phi_i / i \phi_{i,s} \quad (2)$$

where p and p_i^s are the pressure of the system and the saturation pressure of the pure component i at the system temperature, y_i and x_i represent the mole fractions of component i in the vapor and liquid phases, respectively, ϕ_i is the fugacity coefficient of component i in the vapor phase, while ϕ_i^s is the fugacity coefficient of component i in its saturated state. The fugacity coefficients ϕ_i and ϕ_i^s are close to unity at the pressures used in this study, and since the IL is nonvolatile, the vapor phase is only composed of solvent which leads to y_i equal to unity. Thus, the activity coefficient of solvent in solution can be simplified as

$$\gamma = p / p_i^s \quad (3)$$

where subscript i refers to solvents such as water or ethanol. The pure component saturation pressure p_i^s , of water and ethanol were estimated using correlations obtained from DIPPR's database.⁸⁰

The activity coefficients estimated for the studied systems are reported in Table 2 to 8 and depicted in Figure 4 at 0.1 MPa along with the COSMO-RS predictions (for other system pressures, see Figure S2 of the Supporting Information). As depicted in Figure 3, the activity coefficients evidence the behavior observed for the systems boiling temperatures, with the activity coefficients decreasing from the $[\text{SCN}]$ to $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]$ but increasing afterward for the $[\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]$ and $[\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]$. As discussed above, the high polarity of the anion $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ ⁷⁴ leads to a higher capability to establish hydrogen bonds (H-bond donors) leading therefore, to the lowest activity coefficients of the series. Furthermore, as shown previously,⁷⁴ the increase in the number of cyano groups in the series $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$, $[\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]^-$ and $[\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]^-$ leads to a decrease on the ability of these anions to act as H-bond acceptors and

therefore to an increase of the compounds' activity coefficients, as depicted in Figure 3.

For the ethanol-containing mixtures the activity coefficient data suggest that the interactions are weaker than those present in aqueous systems with the deviation to ideality following the trend $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{N}(\text{CN})_2] < [\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{SCN}] < [\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{C}(\text{CN})_3] < [\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]$. The differences between $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]$ and $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{SCN}]$, as well as between $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]$ and $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{im}][\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]$, are, however, less pronounced than those in aqueous systems where the hydrogen bonding is more intense.

4.2. MD Simulations. 4.2.1. Validation of MD Simulations. To complement the experimental part of this study, MD simulations were performed for the systems containing the CN-based ILs and ethanol. For the aqueous systems containing the same ILs, MD simulations were already performed and discussed in a previous study.⁷⁴

Density estimation is usually used to recognize the ability of a force field to reproduce a system.⁸¹ As mentioned in the computational detail section, pure ILs force fields were tested and accordingly to density estimation, they were considered to be able to reproduce the behavior of these pure ILs. In Table S2 of the Supporting Information are compiled values of experimental and simulated densities and enthalpies of vaporization for pure ILs. A good agreement is obtained for density values, but for the values of enthalpies, as expected, differences can reach tens of kJ/mol, associated with the lack of accuracy and difficulty of measuring experimentally this property.³⁹

Furthermore, and using the density data measured in this study for mixtures of CN-based ILs and ethanol, a comparison between experimental data and density values obtained from our simulations was also made, as compiled in Table S1 of Supporting Information. The maximum deviation obtained was in the order of 3%, suggesting that the force fields adopted provide also a good structural description of the mixtures with ethanol.

4.2.2. Radial distribution function and coordination numbers. Radial distribution function, $g(r)$ or RDF, and coordination numbers (Z) are commonly used in MD simulations to evaluate and describe the atomic local structural organization of mixtures. The first gives the probability of finding a particle at the distance r , from another particle (considered the reference), providing a quantitative description of enhancement or depletion of densities of atoms, or groups of atoms, around a selected moiety with respect to bulk values. The second, the coordination number, is the average number of atoms of one type surrounding the reference atom within a cutoff, r_z , given by the integral of RDF. The cutoff is usually

chosen to be the first local minimum of the corresponding RDF. Figure 5 and S3 in the SI, provide all the RDFs for the mixtures considered, and Table 9 compiled the Z numbers estimated for all mixtures and type of interactions.

The analysis of the anion-solvent, cation-solvent, cation-anion, and solvent-solvent interactions were based on the site-to-site RDFs obtained for the N-HO, H1-OH, H1-N, and OH-HO pairs, respectively, where N is the nitrogen atom of each anion, H1 is the acidic proton of the cation, and HO and OH stand for protons and oxygen atoms in the ethanol molecule, respectively.

The first important feature that can be highlighted is the possibility to verify through the obtained RDFs the profile of these interactions, namely the establishment of hydrogen bonds similar to the ones occurring in aqueous systems.⁷⁴ The stronger H-bonds are recognizable by the presence of a site-to-

Figure 1. Isobaric temperature–composition diagram of (a) $[C_4C_{1im}][SCN] + \text{water}$,¹⁸ (b) $[C_4C_{1im}][N(CN)_2] + \text{water}$, (c) $[C_4C_{1im}][C(CN)_3] + \text{water}$, and (d) $[C_2C_{1im}][B(CN)_4] + \text{water}$. The solid lines represent COSMO-RS predictions.

site RDF $Y-H-X$ with a first minimum (r_z) in a distance smaller than 0.26 nm, where Y is an oxygen or nitrogen atom and X an oxygen atom, or weaker H-bonds, presenting a site-site RDF with the first minimum in a distance smaller than 0.40 nm, where Y is an oxygen or nitrogen atom and X a carbon atom.⁸² In the studied systems, the first minimum found was 0.26 and 0.35 nm for anion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions, and cation-solvent and cation-anion interactions, respectively. As mentioned previously, this first minimum is used to estimate the coordination numbers, which are compiled in Table 9.

Additionally, Figure 5 shows that the anion-solvent interaction has a primary role in the interaction occurring between IL and ethanol, which was expected to be common for all CN-based ILs (also observed for aqueous systems), presenting the highest values for the system containing the anion thiocyanate, followed by $[N(CN)_2]^-$, $[C(CN)_3]^-$ and finally $[B(CN)_4]^-$. Ensuing the anion-solvent interaction and in the same solvation shell, the solvent-solvent interactions occur, being predominant in systems containing the anion $[B(CN)_4]^-$. It is worth noting that solvent-solvent interactions depict a double peak of RDF, suggesting the formation of ethanol clustering in all IL + ethanol systems.

In general, the double peak is more pronounced in the system with the anion tetracyanoborate, followed by $[C(CN)_3]^- > [SCN]^- > [N(CN)_2]^-$. This last trend is also observed for the cation-anion interactions occurring at the second solvation shell. Both these latter interactions present the trend that is consistent with the VLE measurements and nonideality as estimated from the activity coefficients. Simultaneously, at contrary to what has been observed for aqueous systems⁷⁴ and the values of $g(r)$ corresponding to the interactions established between cation and the solvent suggest that in the case of IL + ethanol systems they are non-negligible.

A more exhaustive comparison between the different systems is possible by the analysis of the coordination numbers, Z , since their values are obtained by taking into account not only the heights of the first peaks in the RDFs, but also their widths and the densities of the different systems. Thus, the values of Z help to clarify the interaction trend within the CN-based ILs and ethanol, providing important additional information concerning the nature of the interaction between compounds.

Table 9 compiles the calculated coordination numbers for the interactions anion-solvent, cation-solvent, cation-anion, solvent-solvent and finally, IL-solvent. The latter interaction

is the sum of the cation-ethanol and anion-ethanol interactions in all range of concentration, enabling to infer general trends of all involved interactions. The first information that can be taken is the dependence of Z with the mole fraction of IL. Results show that, with the exception of cation-anion interactions, with the increase of IL's mole fraction the interaction of type anionsolvent, cation-solvent and solvent-solvent decrease, as shown by a decrease of the respective Z values. Although these results are a consequence of different densities in each system, they suggest that, with the increase of IL's mole fraction, the frequency of cation-anion interactions also increase, hindering the interaction with ethanol.

From the analysis of the Z values obtained for the IL + ethanol interactions, it arises that the highest values are found for the system with the anion $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$, suggesting more favorable interactions with ethanol, which is in close agreement with the activity coefficients reported in the present study (this was also observed for the aqueous systems with the same ILs). Moreover, with the exception of the anion thiocyanate, the propensity to interact with ethanol suggested from the height of the first peak in the RDFs and by the Z values is $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^- > [\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]^- > [\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]^-$. A similar trend was observed for the aqueous systems, suggesting that an increase of CN-groups in the anion hinders the interaction with polar solvents (water and ethanol), consistent with the nonideality observed in these systems. Additionally, these results are consistent with the CHelpG atomic charges calculated for the nitrogen atoms in the CN groups (the mediators of the interactions between the anion and water or ethanol) which become less negative in the order $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^- > [\text{SCN}]^- > [\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]^- > [\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]^-$,

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respectively, with values of $-0.723 e$, $-0.658 e$, $-0.638 e$, and $-0.487 e$.⁷⁴ The differences in the CHelpG charges are directly related with the symmetry of the anion and with the presence of different central atoms in each anion, i.e., sulfur ($[\text{SCN}]^-$), nitrogen ($[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$), carbon ($[\text{C}(\text{CN})_3]^-$) and boron ($[\text{B}(\text{CN})_4]^-$), which lead to different charge delocalization, and hence, different abilities of the anions to establish H-bonds with water or ethanol molecules. Remarkably, the ordering of the partial charges in the nitrogen atoms from the CN-groups in the anions of the ILs agrees with the ordering obtained for VLE and activity coefficient information suggesting a strong relationship between the two.

4.2.3. Spatial Distribution Function. To further get a tridimensional visualization of how each anion interacts with ethanol, the spatial distribution functions (SDFs, a 3D

representation of the probability of finding a particle at a certain position) were calculated for all considered mixtures and are depicted, by mole fraction of IL, in Figure 6. The SDFs were built and analyzed with the TRAVIS⁸³ considering only the hydrogen atom from the hydroxyl group of ethanol molecules surrounding each anion of the different ILs considered in this study. Isosurfaces for ethanol (ice blue wired surfaces) with the value of $8 \text{ particles}\cdot\text{nm}^{-3}$ was considered, at 0.2 mol fraction of IL.

Recognizable for all systems containing ILs, interactions of ethanol with the CN-based anions are established preferentially with the nitrogen atoms of the cyanide groups. This type of interaction was also previously observed for aqueous systems.⁷⁴ Nevertheless, the volume of the SDFs for ethanol interacting with the different anions (Figure 6) decreases with the increase of the number of CN-groups in the anion, suggesting that in the case of the anions with less CN-groups, the interaction is more likely to occur, which is consistent with previous findings. In conclusion, the results from MD simulations suggest that the increase of the number of CN-groups leads to a decrease of interactions with ethanol. This behavior is similar to what was observed for the aqueous systems and supports the nonideality observed in the VLE and the activity coefficients.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Isobaric VLE data for seven water/ethanol + imidazolium based IL systems containing cyano group at three different pressures were measured in this work. The results indicate that the imidazolium-based ILs studied cause boiling-point elevations of different degrees according to the interaction strengths between water/ethanol and the IL. Using the VLE data, activity coefficients were estimated aiming at evaluating the nonideality of the systems considered in this study. The results obtained suggest that, for both water and ethanol systems, the ability of the anions to interact with the solvent decreases with increasing number of cyano groups, with the system containing the anion $[\text{N}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ presenting the higher ability to establish favorable interactions. MD simulations were performed for systems composed of ethanol and four different ILs having the common imidazolium-based cation. The MD trajectories were used to calculate radial and spatial distribution functions and also coordination numbers, which were used to infer the nature and profile of the interaction established between ethanol and the ILs. Although presenting slightly different trends, all seem to agree and support the experimental findings, along with activity coefficients data, that an increase of the

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